

Synthesis and Reactions of Aminomethyleneketones

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New aminomethyleneketones are prepared and their reactions studied with a view to know their structure. Although they are neutral they form copper derivatives crystallisable from organic solvents and also form ionisable hydrochlorides. These reactions are characteristic of acids as well as bases. No carbonyl derivative could be prepared. A tentative formula which is consistent with such a behaviour is proposed.

FORMYL camphor (I) formed from camphor and formic ester is according to Auwers and Jacobson¹ a pure enol in solid form. In liquid form however the enol content sinks. The enol form of a formyl ketone(III). According to Claisen and Meyerowitz², is the hydroxy methylene form (IV) which accounts for the fairly strong acid character of such ketones.

methylene camphor is seen described in the literature.

The purpose of the work described in this paper was therefore to synthesise new aminomethyleneketones and to study their reactions which might help in the elucidation of their structure.

The following aminomethyleneketones were prepared by treating the corresponding hydroxy

In their study of the kinetics of mutarotation of *d*-hydroxy methylene camphor Bhagwat, Harmalkar and Deshpande³ found that their results could be best interpreted if, in addition to the formyl form (I) and the hydroxymethylene from (II) there is also present in the solution another enol from (V) of the substance.

A substance like amino methylene camphor (VI) which Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair⁴ prepared by the action of ammonia on hydroxy methylene camphor should also, like the latter, be capable of existing in two or more tautomeric forms. No reactions of this substance described in the literature have however any bearing on its structure. Lowry and Southgate⁵, from the U.V. absorption of the substance suggested for it structure (VII), but no chemical evidence supporting such a structure is available. Moreover, no other aminomethyleneketone besides amino

methylene ketones with ammonia under conditions described in the experimental part of the paper.

- (i) amino methylene methyl ethyl ketone (VIII)
- (ii) amino methylene diethyl ketone (IX)
- (iii) amino methylene cyclo hexanone (X)
- (iv) amino methylene menthone (XI)
- (v) amino methylene acetophenone (XII)

(X)

(XI)

(XII)

The above structures are used on the assumption that amino methylene camphor is (VI).

The new amino methylene ketones prepared are solids crystallisable from benzene or methyl alcohol. They are neutral, sparingly soluble in water and give no colour with ferric chloride. They however form copper derivatives which are crystallisable form

benzene and have compositions showing that they are derived from mono basic acids. On shaking with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid the amino methylene ketones slowly dissolve but not completely. On allowing the hydrochloric acid solution to evaporate at room temperature a white crystalline solid separates whose analytical data are in agreement with the composition of a mono hydrochloride. It readily dissolves in water and precipitates silver chloride from silver nitrate. On adding alkali to the aqueous solution of the hydrochloride however the original aminomethylene ketone is not recovered. The nature of the hydrochloric acid reaction is being investigated.

On adding bromine to the solutions of the aminomethylene ketones in chloroform the reagent is rapidly absorbed. But no bromine containing solid product separates. Likewise the usual carbonyl reagents fail to produce a solid derivative.

The I.R. absorption spectra of the aminomethylene ketones (VIII), (IX) and (XII) indicate the presence of hydrogen bonding of the type.

TABLE I

Hydroxy methylene ketone (a)	Amino methylene ketone (b)	Yield of (%)	Analytical data of (b)	Copper derivative	Hydrochloride	
Hydroxy methylene methyl-ethyl ketone ⁶ .	Amino methylene methyl ethyl ketone (VIII). Pale yellow solid. m.p. 108°.	80	Found C, 60.7 H, 9.2 N, 14.3	C ₅ H ₉ ON requires solid. M.P. 131° C, 60.6 H, 9.1 N, 14.1 (C ₅ H ₉ ON) ₂ Cu requires Cu 24.1%.	Green blue crystalline solid. M.P. 131° Found : Cu 24.1 Cu 24.6%.	Hydroscopic crystalline solid, soluble in cold water. Found Cl 26.9 C ₅ H ₉ ON, HCl requires Cl 26.9%.
Hydroxy methylene di-ethyl ketone ⁷ .	Amino methylene diethyl ketone (IX) pale yellow crystalline solid m.p. 128°.	90	Found C, 63.2 H, 9.8 N, 12.9	C ₆ H ₁₁ ON requires solid m.p. 173° C, 63.7 H, 9.8 N, 12.3 (C ₆ H ₁₁ ON) ₂ Cu requires Cu, 22.0%	Green blue crystalline solid m.p. 173° Found Cu 21.7 Cu 22.0%	Hygroscopic crystalline solid, soluble in cold water. Found Cl 24.3 C ₆ H ₁₁ ON, HCl requires Cl 23.5%.
Hydroxy methylene cyclohexanone ⁸ .	Amino methylene cyclohexanone (X) yellowish crystalline so solid m.p. 93°.	80	Found C, 67.2 H, 8.9 N, 11.7	C ₇ H ₁₁ ON requires solid m.p. 146° C, 67.2 H, 8.9 N, 11.2 (C ₇ H ₁₁ ON) ₂ Cu requires Cu 20.5%.	Green blue crystalline solid m.p. 146° Found Cu 20.3 Cu 20.5%.	Hygroscopic solid soluble in water. Found Cl 21.7 C ₇ H ₁₁ ON, HCl requires Cl 21.7%.
Hydroxy methylene menthone ⁹ .	Amino methylene menthone (XI) pale yellow crystalline solid m.p. 88° [α] _D +57.3°.	80	Found C, 72.3 H, 10.4 N, 8.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₉ ON requires which could not be turned into crystalline solid. C, 72.9 H, 10.5 N, 7.7	Brown thick liquid requires which could not be turned into crystalline solid. Found Cu 17.7 Cu 18.0%.	Yellowish crystalline solid soluble in hot water. Found Cl 16.5 C ₁₁ H ₁₉ ON, HCl requires, Cl 16.0%.
Hydroxy methylene aceto phenone ¹⁰ .	Amino methylene aceto phenone (XII) yellowish crystalline solid m.p. 84°.	80	Found C, 73.0 H, 5.8 N, 9.2	C ₉ H ₉ ON requires m.p. 141° C, 73.4 H, 6.1 N, 9.5 (C ₉ H ₉ ON) ₂ Cu requires Cu 18.0%.	Brown crystalline solid m.p. 141° Found Cu 17.7 Cu 18.0%.	Yellowish crystalline solid soluble in hot water. Found Cl 19.8 C ₉ H ₉ ON, HCl requires Cl 19.1%.

R₃

The broadening of the bands 3350 and 3250 cm^{-1} is probably due to intra molecular hydrogen bonding confirmed by the lowering of the normal frequency (methyl amino 3470, 3360 $^{-1}$). The bands at 1660–1865 are in conformity with unsaturated carbonyl group.

Experimental

The hydroxy methylene ketones required for the preparation of the aminomethyleneketones were obtained by treating the ketone (1 mol) with ethyl formate (1 mol) and metallic sodium (1 atom) in dry ether at ice temperature. The sodium salt formed was filtered, dissolved in water and the solution acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The liberated hydroxy methylene ketone, after extraction with ether and removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. Hydroxy methylene methyl-ethyl ketone solidifies on distillation. All others are liquids.

The hydroxy methylene ketone, was mixed with strong aqueous ammonia at ice temperature, and the mixture was allowed to remain for five to six days with occasional shaking. The solid aminomethyleneketone which separated, was filtered, dried and crystallised from hot benzene or methyl alcohol.

Since hydroxy methylene acetophenone is unstable and rapidly undergoes self condensation to form 1 : 3 : 5 tribenzoyl benzene, the crude substance, generated from its sodium derivative was immediately covered with strong aqueous ammonia, before self condensation sets in.

The copper derivatives were prepared by adding neutral aqueous copper acetate to the aqueous alcoholic solution of the aminomethylene ketone. The copper derivative separated almost immediately. It was filtered and crystallised from benzene.

The hydrochlorides were obtained by shaking aminomethylene ketones with strong aqueous hydrochloric acid at ice temperature. The ketones slowly begin to dissolve, but not completely, the solution was filtered and allowed to evaporate at room temperature. Crystals began to separate in the course of a day. They were drained on porous tile, dried and analysed. The crystalline product readily dissolves in water, but on adding excess of alkali the aminomethyleneketone is not regenerated.

In the table are shown

- (i) Hydroxy methylene ketones (a) with references in literature about their preparation.
- (ii) Aminomethyleneketones (b) derived from (a) with properties, yields and probable structures analytical data of the amino methylene ketones, and of their copper derivatives and their hydrochlorides.

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